

Wind-formed Architectural Shapes

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The paper investigates the design loop of parametrically creating an architectural shape based on the analysis of the specific wind situation of the design site, continuously testing the design's performance in the wind using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations and subsequently adjusting the formed architectural shape based on the wind simulations' results. An optimal shape for the determined behavior in the wind is sought in this iterative process. The design strategy is being developed as an attempt to create a sustainable and effective alternative design approach for the changing future environment. The complexity of the process, particularly the need of the repetitive wind tunnel adjustment for every new design situation, or the need of external post-processing software for displaying the wind results of every new architectural shape remains a disadvantage in the search for an optimal architectural solution.

Keywords: *environment, parametric architecture, CFD, performance, wind analysis*

INTRODUCTION

The relationship between the man-created architecture and nature has acquired a greater relevance after the last released assessment report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. IPCC is now 95 percent certain that humans are the main cause of current global warming (Pachauri and Meyer 2014). Edwards (2010) remarks that global warming causes a great deal of regional weather instability e.g. "...the intensity of storms increases, with higher rainfall, stronger winds and less seasonal predictability for countries near to major oceans" (ibid., p.6). Designing for such unpredictable environment requires a closer observation of the environmental conditions

of the place. The natural or artificial scenery, architecture, for instance, has a great influence on the wind pattern, turbulences or acceleration of the wind. A thorough analysis of the design site's specific wind characteristics contributes to the development of a sustainable design solution. In this sense, incorporating the parametric modeling into the design loop has an advantage of including the wind data into the process and generating architecture based on it, and/or based on the desired performance of architecture in the wind. As Shea (2004) mentions, "Lately, through the development of parametric and associative geometry, CAD tools are able to parametrically vary design concepts keeping in step with design in-

tent" (ibid., p. 89).

Architecture vs. natural environment

In the search for the balance between the natural and artificial environment, an inspiration is often found in nature. The natural phenomenon of water and wind erosion that shapes the nature, has been observed and transformed into the simulated erosion of architectural forms made of ice in order to discover new site-specific design strategies that enhance natural ventilation and minimize turbulence around designed building shapes (Demers and Potvin 2016). The investigation of natural ventilation of buildings and the air flow lines have inspired the idea of shape optimization of buildings' interiors. The shape optimization of a room emerges from the CFD analysis of the natural ventilation (Stavridou 2015). These examples show an approach to design that is not only inspired by nature, but it also reacts to the specific character of the environment and benefits from it.

Wind and its effects on the creation of architectural shapes

This paper investigates the wind as one of the environmental factors that influence and 'shape' the architecture. The specific wind situation is a basis for the form generation presented here. An architectural form i) can represent a minimum resistance to the wind flow (e.g. aerodynamic shape), or ii) can concentrate the wind flow and utilize the wind energy, iii) can diffuse the wind flow, iv) can modify the direction of the wind flow by accelerating or deflecting it, or v) can transform an invisible element into a visible one (e.g. wind energy harvesting). The wind-architecture interaction schemes are shown in Figure 1. First two categories defining the wind-architecture interaction, together with an idea of wind energy harvesting, are examined in this paper. Mooneghi and Kargarmoakhar (2016) emphasize that the ultimate goal in the search for an aerodynamic architectural shape should be the true optimum shape and add that "...a systematic approach for taking full advantage of aerodynamic shape optimization for buildings is not fully explored yet" (ibid., p. 231). The

integration of the wind simulation software in the early phase of architectural design is significant in the search for an optimal performance and an evaluation of architecture in the specific wind conditions (Castro Moya 2015; Chronis et al. 2017).

CASE STUDY

The proposed site-specific design approach that incorporates the parametric modeling and the analysis of the design's performance in the wind is presented on a step by step transformation of the industrial site of Loudden Docks in Stockholm, Sweden. EnergyPlus web database, coupled with the statistics from SMHI (Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute) are used as a source of the weather data. Westerly winds are prevailing most of the year, whereas southerly winds reach the highest speeds. Both wind directions are taken into account in the site analysis and in the process of form finding. Next, the wind temperature is observed during the warm seasons. In the spring, the wind temperature is as low as 0-5 degrees for the southerly winds and ranges from 0-20 degrees Celsius for the westerly winds. In autumn, southerly winds have an average temperature of 0-10 degrees, while the westerly winds' temperature is in average 5-15 degrees Celsius. In the summer, the wind temperature can range from 10 to 25 degrees Celsius, depending on the wind direction [1, 3].

Wind flow between cylindrical silos

The abandoned industrial zone called Loudden Docks is around 670 meters long and around 150 meters wide and consists of densely placed concrete silos reaching the height of around 35 meters. The dense distribution of such wind obstacles causes the wind to accelerate between the silos and creates a very turbulent situation around them (see Figures 2 and 3). The simulations of the wind flow are made in Rhino CFD plug-in for Rhino. The advantages and disadvantages of this simulation tool have been analyzed in detail by Chronis et al. (2017). For the westerly and southerly winds, the mean wind speed at the

Figure 1
Five schemes of the
wind-architecture
interaction

Figure 2
Southerly winds in
Loudden Docks
(focus area is in the
circle)

reference height of 10 meters is set to 6 m/s and 9 m/s respectively. The values represent the average annual wind speed in the Stockholm's Arlanda airport and are taken from [1]. The change of the wind speed with the height was approximated using the logarithmic function as a wind profile type (Blocken and Carmeliet 2004). The terrain category is set to "sub-urb, forest, regular large obstacle coverage" which is 0.75 m. The domain size is 1175 x 830 x 175 meters for the westerly winds and 863 x 1137 x 175 meters for the southerly winds. The domain size is created with regards to the best CFD guidelines (Iqbal and Chan 2016). The cutting plane for displaying the results is placed 1.75 m above the ground so the wind flow at the pedestrian level is captured.

Figure 3
Westerly winds in
Loudden Docks
(focus area is in the
circle)

The focus of this paper is put on the area that is displayed in Figures 2 and 3 in the dotted circle. A close up of the situation is shown in Figure 4. The red lines are a schematic illustration of the interaction with the wind around the selected silos, using architecture. The wind, in one case, is intended to be deflected from the two silos and should protect the swimming pools that are proposed inside the silos that are reduced in height. The other two red lines represent where the wind is intended to be accelerated to be utilized for energy harvesting/to become a visible element.

Figure 4
Analysis of southerly and westerly winds and a proposed interaction with the wind

gular buildings, are selected as the location of 'FlowBrane' no.1 (see also Figure 4). The main goal is to protect the cylindrical swimming pools together with the sitting area around them from the cold Swedish winds and wind gusts. Two curves, a fixed and a flexible curve are the basis for the final form. With every newly modified flexible curve, a new 3D shape is formed: i) by moving the control points of the flexible curve in the x and y-direction within the set range, and ii) by affecting the lift height that depends on the perpendicular distance of the two curves along their length. The lift height is a parametric restraint for the tested shapes. For the first shape, the range is set from 3 to 9 meters. This range is modified for the second tested shape; it is from 4 to 12 meters. A lightweight tensile membrane, shielding two swimming pools from the southerly and, at the same time westerly winds is the result (see Figure 6).

Figure 5
Schematic wind flow lines around the group of silos and the desired wind protection

WIND-INDUCED ARCHITECTURE

Around and between the concrete cylindrical silos, designed architectural shapes in this research called 'FlowBranes' work with the wind. These newly formed architectural shapes are proposed to modify the (quite extreme) wind situation.

'FlowBrane' no.1

The form is designed based on the prevailing wind directions in Stockholm: southerly and westerly, [1, 2] and the requirement for the wind deflection in the horizontal and vertical direction (see Figure 5). Three silos, from the southern side covered by three rectan-

Figure 6
'FlowBrane' no.1 - windshield

'FlowBrane' no.2

The second proposed shape behaves in the wind differently. It doesn't intend to avoid or deflect it; on

the contrary, it gathers and concentrates it. Based on the wind flow CFD results of the whole site (see Figures 2 and 3), a group of three silos which support the wind acceleration is selected. The scheme of the desired direction of the concentrated wind is displayed in Figure 5 on the right-hand-side. The principle of Venturi effect is utilized here: when a fluid passes through a constriction, there is an increase in its velocity. The precise shape (see Figure 7) is parametrically controlled to enable an inclusion of the wind simulation results and a consecutive modification of the form. There are three horizontal profile curves created from the tangents to the circles (silos). The tangents represent the desired wind flow; in this case, we want it to be accelerated. The profile curves can be controlled and modified according to the CFD results and thus a new tensile membrane is generated with every change and its performance in the wind can be tested again. The accelerated wind flow can be used for the wind energy harvesting, as well as the materialization of the wind using piezoelectric sticks (see Figure 7).

Figure 7
'FlowBrane' no.2 -
wind accelerator

Wind simulations

Both designs are tensile membranes with a negligible thickness. Rhino CFD would require at least some thickness to be able to detect the mesh and consequently a very fine grid around this mesh so the calculation cells capture it correctly. Hence, another option is examined in this paper. The powerful CFD solver ODS studio which is based on the Linux operating system is now available for the algorithmic plug-

in for Rhinoceros, Grasshopper. This enables to run parametric shape studies and observe their effect on the wind flow. The wind tunnel and mesh settings can be changed very quickly and the solver can calculate multiple wind directions by rotating the geometry. A disadvantage is a need for external software for displaying the results and the fact that the software is still in a beta version. Both 'FlowBranes' are tested using this CFD analysis tool. Almost all presets are used from the 'Virtual wind tunnel' for a 'Simple external CFD' case demonstration provided by ODS engineering [4]. Two different options are tested for both tensile membranes. Based on the wind test results of the first shape, changes are made in the parametric model to obtain the results closer to the desired behavior in the wind. The wind speed of 6 m/s is used for the westerly winds and 9 m/s for the southerly winds for testing 'FlowBrane' no.1. The performance in the wind and its wind-protecting function can be compared in Figure 8. The same scale range was used for all cases, i.e. from 0 to 15 m/s for a better visual comparison.

The wind speed used for testing 'FlowBrane' no.2 is 14 m/s for the simulation of southerly and 11 m/s for the westerly wind gusts. The ability of the designs to accelerate the wind in both wind directions, along with the peak wind velocity can be observed in Figures 9 and 10. The same scale range was used for comparing the results.

DISCUSSION

'FlowBrane' no.1

The wind analysis results of the first generated shape of 'FlowBrane' 1 show that despite it provides a good wind protection of one of the swimming pools in the southerly winds and, in principle, decelerates the wind; it is not efficient enough (see Figure 8). In southerly winds, the wind speed 0.5 m above the surface of one of the pools is as high as 8 m/s. Therefore, a variation of the flexible curve in the parametric model is made and the middle part of the membrane is lifted. The range for the lift height is also changed. The new generated shape appears to cause turbu-

Figure 8 Performance of the two shape modifications of 'FlowBrane' no.1 and no.2 in the southerly winds (left) and westerly (right) winds

lence; however, the wind speed 0.5 m above the surface of the pools is lowered and also the wind speed of the turbulent air is maximum 5 m/s. If this value is not exceeded more than 20% of hours per year, the conditions for outdoor activities are considered acceptable (Standard 2006).

'FlowBrane' no.2

The analysis of two shape modifications of 'FlowBrane' no.2 shows good results for the first design option. The shapes are aerodynamic in the southerly winds and the flow is concentrated and accelerated in the desired way. On the leeward side, the flow gradually decelerates and a turbulent wake is formed (see Figure 9 - top). After the parametric adjustment of shapes, the acceleration of the flow is clearer. However, the shapes are less aerodynamic than in the first case. This causes separation and a turbulent wind

flow (see Figure 9 - bottom). In the westerly winds, the first design option provides a good acceleration of the wind which is then smoothly directed to the sides (see Figure 10 - top). The second design option provides also the desired acceleration, however, the flow path is less smooth and turbulent wake is formed on the leeward side (see Figure 10 - bottom). Both design options are efficient for both wind directions. The southerly and westerly winds are caught and squeezed between the shapes. The CFD analysis catches the differences in the performance and enables an adjustment of the design, using parametric model.

CONCLUSION

The presented case study demonstrates the design approach that incorporates the wind situation, takes into account the specific wind conditions in the re-

Figure 9
Performance of the
two shape
modifications of
'FlowBrane' no.2 in
the southerly winds

gion and based on the performance of the designed shapes retroactively adjusts the parametrically designed architectural shape. The presented design approach is developed as a reaction to the unstable weather conditions caused by global warming. In order to get one step closer to the sustainable designs, the local weather conditions become an important part of the design phase. Moreover, the created architectural shapes are generated based on the intended function of architecture in the wind. This reciprocal relationship between wind and architecture is tested in a case study in extreme urban environment. The microclimate of the place is influenced by the dense urban structure of high concrete cylindrical silos. The wind flow is affected using parametrically created architectural shapes. Two shapes with different functions in the wind are generated in the parametric process and tested in CFD soft-

ware which can capture the thin geometry of membranes correctly. The results are evaluated and the process of the shape generation can be repeated until the desired, optimal performance in the wind is achieved. The wind analysis of a variety of shapes is time-consuming as the meshing, the wind tunnel settings and the calculation settings have to be changed for every new option (Rhino CFD), or every new option has to be loaded in post-processing software (ODS studio). This remains a disadvantage in the form-finding process.

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Figure 10
Performance of the
two shape
modifications of
'FlowBrane' no.2 in
the westerly winds

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